

The Effect of Profit System, Product Trust, Social Group Influence on Member Satisfaction on Nano Herbal Product : Sunpro Propolis

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Abstract:- This study examines the antecedents and outcomes of using Sunpro brand propolis nano-supplements as part (nano-foods) from the perspective of multi-level marketing members. The research investigated the preferences of 375 members who have purchased the supplement repeatedly mainly to maintain their body health. Through structured interviews and questionnaires, the study found that members' satisfaction was not influenced by the profit system, but trust in the product and social group influence were the main drivers affecting multi-level marketing members' satisfaction with the supplement. In addition, peer-to-peer influence is also important in creating awareness and influencing other members to use the supplement.

Keywords:- Multi Level Marketing, Member Satisfaction, Profit System, Trust in the Product, Social Influence Group, Peer-to-Peer Influence.

I. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia, as the largest economic power in Southeast Asia, has experienced significant impacts from the COVID-19 pandemic that began in December 2019. This pandemic has affected various business sectors, especially Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), with a decrease in turnover of up to 78% according to OKE OCE SMEs data. The recession that lasted from the end of 2019 to the end of 2021 hit the Indonesian economy. However, in the second quarter of 2022, the Indonesian economy began to rebound, with Bank Indonesia predicting economic growth between 4.7-5.5% in 2022, supported by global economic improvement, increased domestic demand, and policy stimulus (Bank Indonesia, 2022).

In May 2022, President of the Republic of Indonesia, Joko Widodo, eased regulations to revive the economy, with the community starting to resume normal activities and free to travel provided they have been vaccinated with the third dose. During the pandemic, the community also adopted a healthier lifestyle, including a 51.20% increase in multivitamin consumption in 2020. However, the decrease in people's purchasing power remains a challenge, with a decrease in the purchasing power of farmers and construction workers. In addition, the consumption of

supplements and herbal medicines to maintain body immunity has become a trend in the community. Products such as red ginger, turmeric, galangal, and bee products like honey and propolis have become popular. This is evidenced by the increase in the number of health supplement and herbal products allowed to circulate by the BPOM in 2022. It is estimated that national herbal product sales will reach IDR 23 trillion in 2025, up from IDR 13.8 trillion in 2020.

Propolis, a valuable by-product of the meliponiculture industry, has gained significant attention due to its remarkable pharmacological importance (Chin Kung, 2022). As a complex mixture of resins collected by honey bees from various plant saps, it is further enriched by salivary secretions and enzymes and used for the construction and protection of bee nests (Sahlan, 2021). As of June 2022, there are 790 products registered with the Indonesian Food and Drug Authority (BPOM) that contain propolis (BPOM, 2022). Despite its popularity, 55% of the general public surveyed expressed their dislike for the Multi Level Marketing (MLM) sales system, through which 80% of propolis products are sold.

In 2019, propolis accounted for 10% of the national herbal product market share, a little-known fact due to the dominance of direct MLM sales. Analysis of Google Trends over the past five years shows an increase in searches for propolis and specific brands such as British Propolis, Melia Propolis, and Nasa Propolis. Sunpro Propolis, a PT XYZ product sold exclusively through the MLM system at PT Natural Nusantara, uses nano technology in its production. Despite having advanced production technology, its sales are assumed to be lower than British Propolis due to less search demand. According to 2019 data from PT XYZ, 80% of propolis product sales were conducted through direct sales systems. Concerns have been raised about the familiarity of propolis and the Multi-level Marketing (MLM) sales system among the general public, as it is feared that propolis may only be known within certain circles. Preliminary surveys were conducted to gauge public familiarity with propolis and the MLM system. The results of these surveys will be discussed in this study (PT YXX, 2019).

Customer satisfaction, which is influenced by factors such as perceived acceptability, plays an important role in repurchase and recommendation of a product. Nine acceptance attributes were identified: perceived convenience, perceived benefits, trust in the product, trust in the pharmaceutical company/brand, relative price, social group influence, perceived risk, cultural trust, and salesperson influence (Marimuthu, 2019). These aspects of perceived acceptance impact customer satisfaction and their willingness to recommend a product.

However, there is a lack of research on consumer behavior in communities such as MLM members, and the interest of these members to recommend nanotechnology-based herbal products such as propolis. This study fills this gap by exploring the behavior of MLM members in relation to nanofood products, specifically propolis. Therefore, This study aims to understand the factors influencing the satisfaction of members of PT Natural Nusantara with Sunpro Propolis, a product that experienced a significant sales decline in recent years. A preliminary survey was conducted among 20 members, revealing high satisfaction levels, particularly in terms of trust in the product, social group influence, profit system, and salesperson influence. The research proposes to examine the influence of the profit system, trust in products, and social group influence on member satisfaction with Sunpro Propolis. The study seeks to identify the factors causing the decline in Sunpro Propolis sales and understand the attributes influencing members' intent to recommend the product. The practical contribution of this research is to help the company evaluate its sales strategy for Sunpro Propolis, with the aim of improving overall sales. Theoretically, it aims to provide additional information regarding the variables influencing member satisfaction with Sunpro Propolis sold through the Multilevel Marketing system.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In the realm of consumer behavior and product acceptance, several studies have shed light on various factors that influence consumers' decisions. Malliga Marimuthu (2019) and Hui-Rang Lim & Soyoung An (2021) both explored the acceptance and intention to purchase health-related products, such as herbal food supplements and wellbeing food, respectively. They found that attributes like perceived convenience, benefits, trust in the product and brand, relative price, social group influence, perceived risk, and cultural beliefs significantly affect consumer behavior. Similarly, Chia-Lin Hsu (2017) studied the purchase intention of green skincare products, finding that factors like country of origin and price sensitivity significantly influenced consumers' decisions.

The role of media and social dynamics in influencing consumer behavior was another common theme in the literature. Praew Panvisavas (2019) found that factors like product, price, promotion, place, personalization, privacy, and media exposure all affected purchase intention in M-Commerce of Herbal Products. Guillaume Dumonta & Mart Otsb (2020) also found that positive social media news

about a company's image can enhance personal branding. Reny Nadlifatin & Satria Fadil Persada (2021) further highlighted the influence of social media in their study on millennials' job pursuit intention in multilevel marketing.

Several studies focused on the relationship between customer satisfaction, trust, and loyalty. For instance, Rimawan, Erry., Mustofa, Ali., Mulyanto, Angga Dwi. (2017) and Leninkumar, Vithya. (2017) both found that customer satisfaction significantly influenced customer loyalty. However, they differed in their findings on the role of trust, with Rimawan et al. finding that trust did not affect customer satisfaction or loyalty, while Leninkumar found a significant positive correlation between trust and customer loyalty. Reza Eka Wardhana (2016) also found a significant direct influence of customer experience on customer satisfaction and loyalty.

The impact of service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty was another key focus in the literature. Saling., Modding, Basri., Semmaila, Baharuddin., & Gani, Achmad. (2016) found that service quality had a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions but did not significantly affect customer satisfaction. In contrast, Firdausy, Carunia Mulya., & Idawati, Rani. (2017) found that service quality had a positive and significant effect on the purchase decisions made by Traveloka customers. Wu, J.J., Hwang, J.N., Sharkhuu, O., & Tsogt, O.B. (2018) also highlighted the importance of complementary service quality in shopping online and off-line.

In the context of E-commerce, Al-dweeri et al., (2019) and Falahat, M et. Al (2019) both studied the effect of E-service quality on consumer trust and loyalty. They found a positive relationship between E-Satisfaction, E-Trust, and E-Loyalty, with E-Trust having a positive and significant effect on E-Loyalty.

These studies provide a comprehensive overview of various factors influencing consumer behavior, satisfaction, and loyalty in different contexts. They highlight the importance of factors such as product quality, service quality, trust, price, promotion, and customer experience in shaping customer decisions and loyalty. The findings can be instrumental in informing strategies for businesses seeking to enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Fig 1 Conceptual Model

➤ *This Study is Motivated by the Research of Marimutu (2019) and aims to Develop the following Hypotheses:*

- **H1: Profit System and Member Satisfaction**
Drawing on the work of Aisyah (2020), J. Liu and W.M. Joo (2020), and Lee (2021), it is hypothesized that the profit system, encompassing direct sales profits, Point Value, and Business Value, influences member satisfaction. The higher the profits, the more satisfied the members, and the more likely they are to sell MLM products and develop their network for future passive income.
- **H2: Trust in Products and Member Satisfaction**
Based on the findings of Vithya (2017), Anh (2020), and Reza (2016), it is hypothesized that trust in products, influenced by factors such as product design, brand image, and product certification, affects member satisfaction. Members' experiences with a product can impact their satisfaction and subsequent loyalty.
- **H3: Social Group Influence and Member Satisfaction**
Informed by the research of Nadlifatin (2021) and Crittenden (2004), it is hypothesized that social group influence, driven by the role of Key Opinion Leaders (KOLs) and the quality of social group activities, impacts

member satisfaction. The ability of a leader to influence and accompany their members, coupled with the adaptive capabilities of the salesperson, can create a supportive environment that enhances member satisfaction and growth.

III. METHOD

This study employs a causal research design to analyze the cause-effect relationship between independent variables (Profit System, Trust in Products, and Social Group Influence) and the dependent variable (Member Satisfaction). The independent variables in this study are the Profit System (X1), Trust in Products (X2), and Social Group Influence (X3), while the dependent variable is Member Satisfaction (Y). Subsequently, Each variable is broken down into dimensions, indicators, and measurements, allowing the researcher to determine whether to use the same measurement procedures or develop new ones. These indicators serve as benchmarks for evaluating the practices carried out by the company under study. Thus, the operationalization of research variables refers to the concrete specifications of the research variables that are related to the realization to be measured and the aspects to be observed in the study.

Table 1 Operational Variables

Variable	Dimensions	Indicator	Scale		
Profit System (X1) Nadlifatin (2021)	1. Member margins	a. Have a good balance of buying and selling.	Ordinal		
		b. Maintained consumer selling price practices			
	2. Point Value (PV)	a. Has a high product PV value determination	Ordinal		
		b. Practice through official distributor channels so that PV is recorded			
	3. Business Value (BV)	a. Have a high product BV value determination	Ordinal		
		b. Practice through official distributor channels so that BV is listed			
Trust in Products (X2) Anh (2020)	1. Product Appearance	a. Product design that attracts members	Ordinal		
		b. Members feel comfortable with the material and volume of product packaging.			
	2. Brands	a. Brand known by members			
		b. <i>track record</i> is well known in the member community			
	3. Certification	a. Members feel <i>trust</i> if the product has a BPOM distribution permit			
		b. Members will feel <i>trust</i> if the product has Halal certification from MUI			
	4. member experience	a. Members will <i>trust</i> if they get reliable (scientific) information			
		b. Members will <i>trust</i> if they feel the benefits are like or exceed the information previously received.			
	Social Group	1. Intensity		a. Information in the group is often conveyed repeatedly	Ordinal

<i>Influence (X3)</i> Erkan (2016)		b. Frequency of meeting or interaction between members in a social group	
	2. Quality	a. The information conveyed has appeal for members	
		b. Detailed information conveyed in a communicative way	
	3. Credibility	a. Information conveyed in social groups can be scientifically justified.	
		b. The social group is always supportive of all members	
	4. Benefit	a. Information and communication is carried out for positive education	
		b. Easy information to adopt	
5. Key Opinion Leaders (leaders)	a. Leaders always provide mentoring		
	b. Leaders always help member <i>problem-solvers</i>		
<i>Member Satisfaction (Y)</i> Suhari et al., in Men (2021)	1. Emotional response	a. Satisfied with being an MLM membership	Ordinal
		b. Satisfied using MLM services.	
	2. Response with respect to a particular focus	a. Satisfied with <i>the product knowledge information</i> .	
		b. Satisfied with the education system periodically.	
	3. Response occurs at a certain time (after consumption, after selecting, based on accumulated experience)	a. Satisfied with the variety of products and services in MLM.	
		b. Satisfied with the income generated.	

Source: Author, processed (2022)

IV. RESULT

This study conducted a survey from December 2nd to 20th, 2022, using a digital questionnaire distributed across various WhatsApp groups of PT Natural Nusantara (Nasa) partners. The respondent data, crucial for understanding the background of the participants and interpreting the research results. According to data processing, it revealed that out of all respondents, 375 (or 99%) were registered members of PT Natural Nusantara (Nasa), while the remaining 2 (or 1%) were not. The respondents of this study, were categorised based on their highest level of education. The results showed that 6% of respondents completed primary school, 14% completed junior high school, and 50% completed senior high school. Furthermore, 1% completed a one-year diploma, 2% completed a three-year diploma, and 25% completed an undergraduate degree. In addition, 0.3% of respondents were veterinarians, had doctorates or other qualifications, and 1.1% had master's degrees.

The study's findings, indicate that 99.7% of respondents have purchased Sunpro Propolis at least once, while 99% have consumed propolis. Furthermore, 6.6% of respondents have purchased Sunpro Propolis once, 4.5%

twice, and a significant majority of 88.9% have purchased it more than twice. This research utilizes respondent feedback to comprehend reactions towards the variables under investigation. Response categories are interpreted based on average values, which aid in understanding response tendencies and the conditions of each variable.

➤ *The following Equation is Presented to Calculate the Class Length for each Interval (Supangat, 2007):*

- **$P = X_{max} - X_{min} / b$**
- Description:
- P = Class Length of each Interval
- X_{max} = Maximum Value
- X_{min} = Minimum Value
- R = Range
- b = Number of Classes

In this study, the maximum value of the assessment is five and the minimum value of the study is one, so that if the value is subsumed into the previous equation, the following results are obtained:

$$P=5-15=0,8$$

Based on the results of the calculation of the class length of each interval, Figure 2 presents the classification of the assessment category of the calculated average value, as follows:

Fig 2 Continuum Line

Table 2 Continuum Line

No.	Intervals	Assessment Criteria
1	1.00 - 1.79	Not good
2	1.80 – 2.59	Not good
3	2.60 – 3.39	Pretty good
4	3.40 – 4.19	Good
5	4.20 - 5.00	Very good

➤ Respondents' Responses Regarding the Profit System Variable

In the Profit System variable with a total of 13 statement items. The following presents the overall results regarding the Profit System variable:

Table 3 Recapitulation of Descriptive Analysis of Member Satisfaction Variables

No	Statement Points	Respondent Answer Score					Total Score	Means
		5	4	3	2	1		
1	I feel satisfied to be a member / partner / stockist of PT Natural Nusantara	336	28	8	3	2	1824	4.84
		89.12%	7.43%	2.12%	0.80%	0.53%		
2	I am satisfied with PT Natural Nusantara's service to members/partners/stockists	325	31	16	2	3	1804	4.79
		86.21%	8.22%	4.24%	0.53%	0.80%		
3	I am satisfied with the product knowledge information provided to members / partners / stockists	304	44	23	4	2	1775	4.71
		80.64%	11.67%	6.10%	1.06%	0.53%		
4	I am satisfied with the education system at PT Natural Nusantara which is held for members / partners / stockists	321	37	15	3	1	1805	4.79
		85.15%	9.81%	3.98%	0.80%	0.27%		
5	I am satisfied with the variety of products and services offered by PT Natural Nusantara	322	39	10	2	4	1804	4.79
		85.41%	10.34%	2.65%	0.53%	1.06%		
6	I am satisfied with the income I generate as a member / partner / stockist of PT Natural Nusantara	261	64	36	9	7	1694	4.49
		69.23%	16.98%	9.55%	2.39%	1.86%		
Total Score and Average						10706	4.73	

Source: Data Processing (2022)

Based on Table 3, it can be seen that the average respondent's response regarding the Member Satisfaction variable is 4.73, including the total score of 10706, which means it is in a very good category.

The score interpretation criteria on the Member Satisfaction variable can be seen in Figure 3 as follows.

Fig 3 Member Satisfaction Variable Continuum Line
Source: Data Processing (2022)

Figure 3 shows that respondents' responses regarding the Member Satisfaction variable are in the very good category with an average value of 4.73 which is in the range 4.20 - 5.00.

➤ *Verification Statistical Analysis*

In this verification analysis, it is related to the formation of a structural equation model, which will then be

tested for hypotheses using the PLS-SEM method. According to Hair et al (2019) the PLS-SEM method estimates complex models with many constructs, indicator variables, and structural paths without imposing distributional assumptions on the data. The following is the PLS-SEM model in this study.

Fig 4 Conceptual Diagram of the PLS-SEM Model

➤ *Testing Outer Model (Measurement Model)*

• *Convergent Validity*

Convergent validity is a test of construct validity. An indicator is said to have good validity if it has value *loading factor* greater than 0.70. However, a loading value of 0.5 to 0.60 is considered sufficient (Chin 1998 in Ghazali, 2014), so that it can be used in research. Based on the estimation results using the help of the SmartPLS 3 program application is obtained *output* model testing as follows.

Fig 5 Value Diagram *Loading Factor Evaluation Outer Model*
Source: Data Processing (2023)

Based on the results of model testing, the results show that all manifest (observed variables) have value *loading factor* greater than 0.6. So the SEM-PLS model is said to have good construct validity. The following is a table showing the values *loading factor* in detail on the models.

Table 4 Loading Factor

Construct	Loading Factor	R critical	Criteria (Loading Factor ≥ 0,6)
X1.1 <- Profit System (X1)	0,736	0,6	Valid
X1.2 <- Profit System (X1)	0,880	0,6	Valid
X1.3 <- Profit System (X1)	0,840	0,6	Valid
X2.1 <- Trust in Product (X2)	0,767	0,6	Valid
X2.2 <- Trust in Product (X2)	0,811	0,6	Valid
X2.3 <- Trust in Product (X2)	0,936	0,6	Valid
X2.4 <- Trust in Product (X2)	0,923	0,6	Valid
X3.1 <- Social Group Influence (X3)	0,692	0,6	Valid
X3.2 <- Social Group Influence (X3)	0,819	0,6	Valid
X3.3 <- Social Group Influence (X3)	0,897	0,6	Valid
X3.4 <- Social Group Influence (X3)	0,900	0,6	Valid
X3.5 <- Social Group Influence (X3)	0,825	0,6	Valid
Y1 <- Member Satisfaction (Y)	0,923	0,6	Valid
Y2 <- Member Satisfaction (Y)	0,927	0,6	Valid
Y3 <- Member Satisfaction (Y)	0,879	0,6	Valid

Source: Data Processing (2023)

Table 4 shows the values *loading factor* for each construct of each variable. Based on the table it can be seen that all *loading factor* worth more than 0.6. So it can be concluded that based on each construct in the study has good validity. Next will be testing *average variance extracted* (AVE) to further strengthen the results of *convergent validity* with criteria when the AVE value ≥ 0.5 (Hair et al, 2019), then the construct used in the study is valid. Here are presented the test results *average variance extracted* using the PLS 3.0 program:

Table 5 Value Average Variance Extracted

To leave	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	R critical	Criteria (AVE ≥ 0.5)
Profit System (X ₁)	0,674	0,5	Valid
Trust in Product (X ₂)	0,744	0,5	Valid
Social Group Influence (X ₃)	0,689	0,5	Valid
Member Satisfaction (AND)	0,828	0,5	Valid

Source: Data Processing (2023)

Based on Table 5 it can be seen the results *convergent validity* based on value *average variance extracted*. These results indicate that all latent variables have an AVE value of more than 0.5. This indicates that the indicators that form the latent construct have *convergent validity* which is good when seen from the value *average variance extracted*.

• *Discriminant Validity Test*

This testing process is carried out to measure how far a construct is really different from other constructs.

Testing *discriminant validity* done through analysis *Fornell-Lacker Criterion* namely the validity test is done by comparing the correlation between variables or constructs with the square root of *Average Variance Extracted* ($\sqrt{}$). The prediction is said to have a good AVE value if the AVE square root value of each latent variable is greater than the correlation between other latent variables. Here is a table *Fornell-Lacker Criterion*:

Table 6 Fornell Larcker Criterion

	Member Satisfaction (Y)	Profit System (X1)	Social Group Influence (X3)	Trust in Product (X2)
Member Satisfaction (Y)	0,910			
Profit System (X1)	0,255	0,821		
Social Group Influence (X3)	0,753	0,238	0,830	
Trust in Product (X2)	0,511	0,243	0,548	0,862

Based on test results *discriminant validity* through *fornell-lacker criterion* it can be seen that the AVE root ($\sqrt{}$) for each construct is greater than the correlation of each construct with other constructs. Another method that can be used to measure *discriminant validity* is through analysis *cross-loading* between the indicators and their constructs, namely by comparing the correlation of the indicators with the constructs associated with the correlation coefficient with other constructs. The correlation

coefficient value of the indicator to the association construct must be greater than the other constructs. The following are the results of the analysis *cross-loading* from research data:

Table 7 Validity Test Value *Cross Loading Discrimination*

	Profit System (X1)	Trust in Product (X2)	Social Group Influence (X3)	Member Satisfaction (Y)
X1,1	0,736	0,139	0,149	0,168
X1,2	0,880	0,233	0,214	0,225
X1,3	0,840	0,214	0,215	0,227
X2,1	0,152	0,767	0,394	0,310
X2,2	0,258	0,811	0,478	0,469
X2,3	0,231	0,936	0,500	0,489
X2,4	0,182	0,923	0,503	0,462
X3,1	0,194	0,397	0,692	0,382
X3,2	0,171	0,433	0,819	0,527
X3,3	0,214	0,521	0,897	0,698
X3,4	0,191	0,466	0,900	0,669
X3,5	0,219	0,451	0,825	0,744
Y1	0,228	0,482	0,697	0,923
Y2	0,203	0,491	0,699	0,927
Y3	0,266	0,422	0,659	0,879

Source: Data Processing (2023)

Based on Table 7 it can be seen that all indicators have a high correlation with the construct compared to other constructs. So it can be concluded that the research model has good discriminant validity at *discriminant validity cross loading*.

• *Test Reliability*

Cronbach's Alpha and *Composite Reliability* to determine whether or not the construct reliability is good. Each construct is said to be reliable if it has *Cronbach's Alpha* and *Composite Reliability* which is greater than 0.70 (Hair et al, 2017) can be said to be reliable, but if *Cronbach's Alpha* and *Composite Reliability* which is greater than 0.60 can still be said to be reliable. Here are presented the test results *reliability* using the Smart PLS 3.0 program.

Table 8 Value *Cronbach's Alpha* and *Composite Reliability*

Latent	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>Composite Reliability</i>
<i>Profit System (X₁)</i>	0,758	0,860
<i>Trust in Product (X₂)</i>	0,884	0,920
<i>Social Group Influence (X₃)</i>	0,887	0,917
<i>Member Satisfaction (AND)</i>	0,896	0,935

Source: Data Processing (2023)

Based on Table 8 it can be seen that there are latent constructs that have value *cronbach's alpha* more than 0.6, this indicates that the latent construct has *reliability* the good one. Apart from that on value *composite reliability* all latent constructs also have a value greater than 0.60. Based on value *cronbach's alpha* and *composite reliability* obtained, indicates that the model has good reliability.

➤ *Structural Model Testing (Inner Model)*

Evaluation of the inner model is an analysis of the results of the relationship between constructs. Inner model testing consists of R square, f square, *Q-square predictive relevance*, and test the hypothesis.

• *R Square*

Furthermore, based on the test results with SmartPLS 3., the following R Square results are obtained.

Table 9 R Square

	<i>R Square</i>	Strong Relationship
<i>Member Satisfaction (AND)</i>	0,585	Strong

Source: Data Processing (2023)

According to Chin (1998) in Yamin and Kurniawan (2011:21), R Square with a value of 0.67 indicates a strong model, a value of 0.33 indicates a moderate model and a value of 0.19 indicates a weak model. From the results of Table 9 it can be seen that the R-Square for variables *Member Satisfaction (Y)* of 0.585 which means that *Profit System (X₁)*, *Trust in Product (X₂)*, and *Social Group Influence (X₃)* simultaneously affect the *Member Satisfaction (Y)* of 58.5%, while the remaining 41.5% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

• *F Square*

Next is to look at the value of *fSquare*. Nilai *fSquare* of 0.02 indicates a small rating, an Effect Size of 0.15 indicates a medium rating and an Effect Size of 0.35

indicates a large rating (Cohen, 1988 in Yamin and Kurniawan (2011: 21). Based on the test results with SmartPLS 3, the F Square results are as follows.

Tabel 10 F Square

Variable	Effect Size	Rating
Member Satisfaction (AND)		
<i>Profit System (X₁)</i>	0,009	Small
<i>Trust in Product (X₂)</i>	0,028	Small
<i>Social Group Influence (X₃)</i>	0,735	Big

Source: Data Processing (2023)

Based on Table 10 shows that variable *Profit System (X₁)*, *Trust in Product (X₂)*, and *Social Group Influence (X₃)* each has an influence with small and large categories in influencing variables *Member Satisfaction (AND)*. variable *Profit System (X₁)*, *Trust in Product (X₂)* each has an influence with a small category in influencing the variables *Member Satisfaction (Y)*, and *Social Group Influence (X₃)* has an influence with a large category in influencing variables *Member Satisfaction (AND)*.

• *Q² Predictive Relevance*

Testing *Q-square* used to measure how well the observed values produced by the model and also the parameter estimates. Mark *Q-square* greater than 0 (zero) indicates that the model has value *predictive relevance*, whereas *Q-square* less than 0 (zero) indicates that the model lacks *predictive relevance* (Cohen, 1988 in Yamin and Kurniawan (2011:21). *Q-valuesquare* which is obtained using the value of *R²* in the table above, the following calculation results are obtained:

Table 11 *Q² Predictive Relevance*

Variable	R Square	1-R Square
<i>Member Satisfaction (AND)</i>	0,585	0,415
<i>Q² =</i>	$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - 0,585) = 58,5\%$	
<i>Error =</i>	$Q^2 = 100\% - 58,5\% = 41,5\%$	

Source: Data Processing (2023)

Based on the calculation results above it is known that the value *Q square* greater than 0, this means that the observed values have been reconstructed properly so that the model has predictive relevance. This means that there is a 58.5% relative effect of the structural model on observational measurements for endogenous latent variables, and as much as 41.5% is a model error.

• *Hypothesis Test*

Hypothesis testing in this study was carried out using the path coefficient, t-value, and p-value. To assess the significance and predictions in hypothesis testing can be seen from the value *path coefficient* and *t-value* (Kock, N. 2016). According to Kock, N (2016) assessing predictions and significance in hypothesis testing can be seen *p-value*. The t-table values can be seen in the following table.

Table 12 T-table Values

	<i>One tailed</i>	<i>Two tailed</i>
t-table	1.64	1.96

✓ According to Kock, N. (2016), with a confidence level of 95% (alpha 5%), two tailed, the following t-table values are obtained:

- If the t-statistic value is > 1.96 (used for direct influence), then H₀ rejected and H₁ accepted.
- If the t-statistic value < 1.96 (used for direct effect), then H₀ accepted and H₁ rejected.

The magnitude of the significance value between the variables tested is presented in the form of the value contained in the arrow that connects one of the variables to the variable that is the goal.

Fig 6 Structural Models (Path Coefficient, Beta)

Fig 7 Significance Value (t-count)

Source: Data Processing Output using Smart PLS (2023)

➤ *Influence Profit System to Member Satisfaction Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara*

The first research hypothesis reads: “*profit system influencemember satisfaction Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara*”. And from this hypothesis it is developed into a statistical hypothesis as follows:

$H_{1.1}: c_1 \neq 0$: *profit system influencemember satisfaction Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara.*

Furthermore, based on the hypothesis above, a hypothesis test was carried out using the method *bootstrapping* using SmartPLS software, and the following values are obtained:

Table 13 Path Coefficient and t-Calculate Influence *Profit System* to *Member Satisfaction* Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara

Influence	Original Sample (O)	t-Statistics	p-value	Conclusion
<i>profit system</i> to <i>member satisfaction</i> Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara	0,064	1,721	0,086	Thank $H_{0,1}$

Source: Data Processing (2023)

From the results of Table 13 above, the value is obtained *Original Sample* (O) which is equal to 0.064 indicates that the direction of influence *profit system* to *member satisfaction* Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara is positive or unidirectional, meaning the better *profit system* then increasing *member satisfaction* Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara. Influence *profit system* to *member satisfaction* Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara is not significant, with a t-statistic value of 1.721 which is less than the t table or 1.721 < 1.96, and the value *p value* of 0.086 greater than alpha 5% (0.05). Thus, $H_{1,1}$ rejected mean ***profit system* not affect *member satisfaction* Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara.**

- Influence *Trust in Product* to *Member Satisfaction* Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara

The second research hypothesis reads: "*trust in products* influence *member satisfaction* on PT Natural Nusantara's Sunpro Propolis product. And from this hypothesis it is developed into a statistical hypothesis as follows:

$$H_{1,2}: c_2 \neq 0: \text{Trust in products influence member satisfaction Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara.}$$

Furthermore, based on the hypothesis above, a hypothesis test was carried out using the method *bootstrapping* using SmartPLS software, and the following values are obtained:

Table 14 Path Coefficient and t-Calculate Influence *Trust in Product* to *member satisfaction* Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara

Influence	Original Sample (O)	t-Statistics	p-value	Conclusion
<i>Trust in Product</i> to <i>member satisfaction</i> Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara	0,131	2,087	0,037	Reject $H_{0,2}$

Source: Data Processing (2023)

From the results of Table 14 above, the value is obtained *Original Sample* (O) which is equal to 0.131 indicates that the direction of influence *trust in product* to *member satisfaction* Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara is positive or unidirectional, meaning the better *trust in product* then increasing *member satisfaction* Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara. Influence *trust in product* to *member satisfaction* Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara is significant, with a t-statistic value of 2.087 greater than t table or 2.087 > 1.96, and a value *p value* of 0.037 smaller than alpha 5% (0.05). Thus, $H_{1,2}$ accepted meaning ***trust in product* influence *member satisfaction* Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara.**

- Influence *Social Group Influence* to *Member Satisfaction* Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara

The third research hypothesis reads: "*social group influence* influence *member satisfaction* Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara". And from this hypothesis it is developed into a statistical hypothesis as follows:

$$H_{1,3}: c_3 \neq 0: \text{social group influence influence member satisfaction Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara.}$$

Furthermore, based on the hypothesis above, a hypothesis test was carried out using the method *bootstrapping* using SmartPLS software, and the following values are obtained:

Table 15 Path Coefficient and t-Calculate Influence *Social Group Influence* to *member satisfaction* Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara

Influence	Original Sample (O)	t-Statistics	p-value	Conclusion
<i>Social group influence</i> to <i>member satisfaction</i> Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara	0,666	12,798	0,000	Reject $H_{0,3}$

Source: Data Processing (2023)

From the results of Table 15 above, the value is obtained *Original Sample* (O) which is equal to 0.666 indicates that the direction of influence *social group influence* to *member satisfaction* Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara is positive or unidirectional, meaning the better *social group influence* then increasing *member satisfaction* Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara. Influence *social group influence* to *member satisfaction* Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara is significant, with a t-statistic value of 12.798 greater than t table or 12.798 > 1.96, and a value *p value* of 0.000 smaller than alpha 5%

(0.05). Thus, $H_{1,3}$ accepted meaning ***social group influence* influence *member satisfaction* Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara.**

V. CONCLUSION

➤ *Based on the Results of the Analysis and Discussion Described in the Previous Chapter, the Conclusions of this Study are as follows:*

- The profit system does not affect member satisfaction with Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara. This can be caused because members are used to using Sunpro Propolis products because of their efficacy, so they no longer consider the benefits of PV, BV or product sales margins.
- Trust in product affects member satisfaction with Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara positively and significantly. Thus, the higher the member's trust, the more satisfied the members feel with the efficacy of Sunpro Propolis and PT Natural Nusantara's services.
- Social group influence affects member satisfaction with Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara positively and significantly. The stronger the influence of the social group, the more satisfied the members are with Sunpro Propolis PT Natural Nusantara. In this case, the members are happy with the social community formed under PT Natural Nusantara, so this results in the members also having a good relationship with the leaders and other members.

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APPENDIX OF OUTPUT SMARTPLS

Table 16 Outer Loadings

	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)
X1.1 <- Profit System (X1)	0,081	8,689
X1.2 <- Profit System (X1)	0,027	33,380
X1.3 <- Profit System (X1)	0,038	22,455
X2.1 <- Trust in Product (X2)	0,043	17,858
X2.2 <- Trust in Product (X2)	0,032	25,093
X2.3 <- Trust in Product (X2)	0,013	70,254
X2.4 <- Trust in Product (X2)	0,016	56,586
X3.1 <- Social Group Influence (X3)	0,043	16,402
X3.2 <- Social Group Influence (X3)	0,032	26,133
X3.3 <- Social Group Influence (X3)	0,017	53,461
X3.4 <- Social Group Influence (X3)	0,017	53,639
X3.5 <- Social Group Influence (X3)	0,031	26,667
Y1 <- Intention to Recommend (Y)	0,029	30,093
Y2 <- Intention to Recommend (Y)	0,041	20,146
Y3 <- Intention to Recommend (Y)	0,023	38,609
Z1 <- Member Satisfaction (Z)	0,015	61,711
Z2 <- Member Satisfaction (Z)	0,018	51,736
Z3 <- Member Satisfaction (Z)	0,027	32,514

Table 17 Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Intention to Recommend (Y)	0,829	0,846	0,897	0,744
Member Satisfaction (Z)	0,896	0,899	0,935	0,828
Profit System (X1)	0,758	0,803	0,858	0,671
Social Group Influence (X3)	0,887	0,906	0,917	0,691
Trust in Product (X2)	0,884	0,905	0,920	0,744

Table 18 Cross Loadings

	Intention to Recommend (Y)	Member Satisfaction (Z)	Profit System (X1)	Social Group Influence (X3)	Trust in Product (X2)
X1.1	0,126	0,168	0,706	0,148	0,139
X1.2	0,263	0,224	0,888	0,214	0,232
X1.3	0,257	0,227	0,852	0,216	0,213
X2.1	0,325	0,310	0,153	0,395	0,769
X2.2	0,454	0,469	0,262	0,477	0,808
X2.3	0,482	0,490	0,233	0,500	0,937

X2.4	0,495	0,462	0,183	0,504	0,925
X3.1	0,423	0,382	0,198	0,705	0,398
X3.2	0,454	0,527	0,173	0,823	0,433
X3.3	0,560	0,698	0,215	0,895	0,521
X3.4	0,547	0,669	0,190	0,899	0,465
X3.5	0,541	0,744	0,219	0,817	0,450
Y1	0,859	0,657	0,273	0,548	0,412
Y2	0,829	0,500	0,218	0,431	0,391
Y3	0,898	0,688	0,221	0,589	0,524
Z1	0,693	0,925	0,230	0,693	0,481
Z2	0,672	0,927	0,202	0,693	0,490
Z3	0,606	0,877	0,268	0,655	0,421

Table 19 Path Coefficients

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Member Satisfaction (Z) -> Intention to Recommend (Y)	0,548	0,528	0,090	6,120	0,000
Profit System (X1) -> Intention to Recommend (Y)	0,072	0,072	0,040	1,790	0,074
Profit System (X1) -> Member Satisfaction (Z)	0,064	0,061	0,038	1,683	0,093
Social Group Influence (X3) -> Intention to Recommend (Y)	0,094	0,106	0,073	1,286	0,199
Social Group Influence (X3) -> Member Satisfaction (Z)	0,659	0,652	0,049	13,460	0,000
Trust in Product (X2) -> Intention to Recommend (Y)	0,169	0,175	0,064	2,639	0,009
Trust in Product (X2) -> Member Satisfaction (Z)	0,134	0,140	0,060	2,246	0,025

Table 20 Specific Indirect Effects

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Profit System (X1) -> Member Satisfaction (Z) -> Intention to Recommend (Y)	0,035	0,034	0,024	1,490	0,137
Social Group Influence (X3) -> Member Satisfaction (Z) -> Intention to Recommend (Y)	0,361	0,345	0,070	5,159	0,000
Trust in Product (X2) -> Member Satisfaction (Z) -> Intention to Recommend (Y)	0,074	0,072	0,031	2,357	0,019

Table 21 R Square

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Intention to Recommend (Y)	0,561	0,556
Member Satisfaction (Z)	0,578	0,574

Table 22 F-Square

	Intention to Recommend (Y)	Member Satisfaction (Z)
Member Satisfaction (Z)	0,289	
Profit System (X1)	0,011	0,009
Social Group Influence (X3)	0,008	0,708
Trust in Product (X2)	0,043	0,029